

An Analysis of Change Point Detection in High Performance Computing

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Abstract— As high-performance computing approaches the Exa-scale era, the analysis of the vast amount of monitoring data generated by supercomputers has become increasingly challenging for data analysts. The detection of change points, which plays a critical role in anomaly detection, performance optimization, and root cause analysis of problems and failures, has grown beyond human capacity for manual review. To address this issue, our focus lies in developing an effective model capable of identifying anomalous behavior, and to achieve this, we introduce the concept of an online adaptive sampling algorithm. By evaluating the model's performance across various use cases, we explore its potential to detect change points. To validate its efficacy, we conduct tests on a complex dataset obtained from Brookhaven National Laboratory. Overall, we observe that the model successfully captures key features of normal behavior, and we believe it opens promising avenues for further research, particularly in assisting with various tasks related to anomaly detection and performance optimization in high-performance computing environments.

Keywords—Change point detection, HPC and Molecular Dynamics (MD)

I. OBJECTIVES

The scientific simulations and application faces data reduction challenges due to the dynamics of large-scale molecular and materials systems, which involve numerous time steps generating sequences of structures. Scientific requirements necessitate calculations on systems containing many atoms, ranging from tens of thousands to millions for molecular dynamics simulations. To meet these science challenges, the application performs dynamics simulations on massive atomistic complexes, comprising millions of atoms, over extended time scales of up to microseconds, with a time resolution of femtoseconds. A single simulation generates an enormous 32 PB of data, making it impractical to store all data for offline analysis. However, within this vast amount of data lies crucial statistical information related to free energies of processes and critical events. These key events include transition states and equilibrium structures, where reactions occur and stable molecules are present, respectively. Preserving this scientifically important data while significantly reducing the data volume is essential. In response to this challenge, we propose a manifold-based learning algorithm designed to filter and extract these key events. By leveraging the algorithm's capabilities, we aim to achieve substantial data reduction while retaining the essential information needed for scientific analysis and understanding of molecular and materials systems dynamics.

II. MOTIVATION

Modern scientific simulations and experiments often involve complex systems with millions of atoms, leading to the generation of vast amounts of molecular dynamics (MD) trajectories data, reaching scales of tens of petabytes (PB). Handling and analyzing such massive datasets present significant challenges for data storage, processing, and analysis. The primary motivation of our research is to develop an efficient approach that reduces the data footprint while

preserving critical information within MD trajectories. Our goal is to retain essential scientific events and insights without compromising data accuracy.

III. PROPOSED RESEARCH AND ITS CHALLENGES

To achieve our goal, we propose an innovative online adaptive sampling algorithm (OAS). This approach involves evaluating the effectiveness of existing data reduction techniques and integrating them into an existing framework. In contrast to traditional offline data reduction methods that may blindly discard valuable information, our proposed approach dynamically selects and stores relevant data points during the simulation, based on key criteria or events. This real-time data selection allows for a more targeted and efficient reduction of the data volume, ensuring that essential scientific insights are preserved.

Challenges: Throughout our investigation, we encountered several challenges in the field of change point detection in HPC. Some of the key challenges and the approaches we used to overcome them are as follows:

- a. **Scalability:** The high volume and dimensionality of HPC datasets poses scalability issues for traditional algorithms. We designed and implemented parallel algorithms that efficiently distributed the workload across multiple processing units, allowing us to handle large datasets effectively.
- b. **Noise and Uncertainty:** HPC datasets often contain noise and uncertainties, making it challenging to distinguish true change points from random fluctuations. We incorporated statistical techniques and regularization methods to enhance the robustness of our change point detection approaches.
- c. **Validation:** Evaluating the performance of change point detection algorithms requires reference samples, which is challenging to obtain in real-world scenarios.

We employed synthetic data with known change points and performed extensive cross-validation to validate the accuracy of our algorithms.

- d. **Containerization challenges:** Our experience with Singularity containers was marred by compatibility issues stemming from our HPC cluster's current operating system. However, we devised a solution to tackle this problem by creating two distinct containers that incorporated MPI and ADIOS. By establishing separate containers with specialized functionalities, we successfully enabled seamless communication between our applications.

IV. COMPUTATIONAL RESOURCES AND FACILITIES

Our proposed online adaptive sampling algorithm was implemented in Python 3.8.10, with initial testing planned at Brookhaven National Laboratory's High-performance computing (HPC) cluster and NSERC Perlmutter as part of the SRP-HPC program. We also implemented parallel ADIOS writer in NWChem and parallel ADIOS reader in analysis algorithm (ADIOS Version 2, [2]), which was wrapped in our Python interface.

Datasets: Collision datasets/NWChem

Preliminary Results: Our initial investigations resulted promising preliminary results on Collision datasets by applying the Kernel Cumulative Sum and KL-CPD (Kernel Change-Point Detection) algorithms. The evaluation demonstrates the effectiveness of the change-point detection (CPD) techniques in terms of performance and accuracy. The preliminary findings indicate that the OAS algorithm effectively captures essential information from the MD trajectories while considerably reducing the data volume. Due to time limitations and work-in-progress, we presented the results tested with one use case called Collision dataset is shown in Fig.1, we plan to include more complex datasets to validate our proposed research.

Figure 1. CPD Visualization

V. CONCLUSIONS/IMPACT OF THE WORK

We propose online streaming adaptive sampling of MD trajectories implemented with ADIOS writer and reader for tighter integration within analysis workflow. We tested our proposed algorithm at BNL HPC Cluster, and we plan to test our proposed algorithms on diverse experimental conditions at supercomputing environments.

In summary, our research addresses the critical challenge of data reduction in MD trajectories generated by scientific simulations with vast amounts of atomistic interactions. The proposed online adaptive sampling framework shows promising potential in effectively reducing the data footprint while retaining essential scientific insights. By optimizing data storage and analysis, our approach can significantly benefit high-performance computing environments, enabling more efficient utilization of resources for molecular dynamics simulations and opening new possibilities for scientific discovery.

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